

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENSURING INTER-ETHNIC HARMONY AND SOLIDARITY IN SOCIETY AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

Isomiddinov Khakimjon Joraboyevich

Independent researcher of Fergana State University

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Abstract: The article examines the importance and future prospects of ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity in the society, its necessity, current issue, and in this process, its socio-philosophical, moral, spiritual, legal classification and specific features are analyzed.

Key words: society, interethnic harmony, solidarity, socio-philosophical, moral, spiritual, legal, future perspectives.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, ensuring inter-ethnic and inter-confessional solidarity, harmony of citizens, strengthening friendly, equal and mutually beneficial relations with foreign countries is considered as one of the priorities of state policy. The large-scale reforms in all spheres are evidence of the noble goal of further raising the standard of living of our people. After all, the interests of citizens can be ensured only by creating an atmosphere of peace and tranquility, mutual respect, kindness and solidarity.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

On the importance and socio-philosophical content of ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity in society, N. Jorayev, S. Safoyev, A. Jalilov, R. Jumayev, N. Mamanazarov, Q. Jorayev, R. Murtazayeva, R. Researchers such as Ubaidullayeva, I. Ergashev, H. Yunusova, V. Gentshke conducted scientific research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The idea of respecting human dignity, freedom of belief and value, and recognizing his rights and freedoms as the highest value is expressed in the wide-ranging reforms being carried out in our country, and in the adopted laws and regulations. In particular, it is noteworthy that the main goal and principle of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at ensuring the guarantees of the rights and freedoms of every citizen.

The development strategy of the new Uzbekistan aimed to achieve 100 goals within the framework of 7 priority areas of development of Uzbekistan in the next 5 years. Efforts to achieve these goals are also clear. They, in turn, make it much easier to control efficiency and effectiveness. In other words, a system was introduced to evaluate the effectiveness of the planned reforms in accordance with the level of achievement of the goals of development.

The 74th goal of the fifth direction of the development strategy - Ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level envisages strengthening the atmosphere of inter-ethnic harmony and inter-religious tolerance in the society. It specifies the implementation of the assigned tasks.

In today's information space, it is an important task to illuminate the principles of tolerance in religions, especially world religions, and to inculcate them in the minds of young

people. Therefore, religious tolerance is the most effective factor in ensuring mutual tolerance between representatives of different religions.

Uzbekistan's national policy model is also reflected in its activities in the field of foreign policy. Our republic actively participates in the process of developing principles on the issue of ensuring the rights of ethnic units in the international arena, implementing international agreements on the protection of the rights and freedoms of nations and peoples.

In particular, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of Uzbekistan, the International Convention on the Elimination of All Types of Racial Discrimination, the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of Genocide Crimes, Nationality, Ethnicity, the fact that he signed a number of documents, such as the declaration on the rights of persons belonging to a minority group in terms of religion or language, also determines the scope of actions in this direction.

Tolerance is a concept that represents people who are kind, caring, generous, and generous to others, who have such spiritual qualities. Tolerance means respecting other people's worldview, religious beliefs, national and ethnic characteristics, traditions, not allowing discrimination and insults in dealings, considering humanity above all else, in the community, means to observe it in interpersonal relationships, in public places. This concept means that people of different religions, belonging to different nationalities and peoples live in harmony and peace within the framework of a single state. At the same time, tolerance as a worldview is opposed to extremism, which is a manifestation of violence. The attitude of tolerance towards the characteristics of different peoples, nationalities and religions in the society can be seen in the example of Uzbekistan. Tolerance is characteristic of some individuals or a whole nation. Tolerance is manifested in national and religious colors. National tolerance means interethnic harmony, while religious tolerance means living in harmony between people of different religious denominations.

Tolerance means respecting the national values, traditions and customs of different cultures, peoples of the world. Such tolerance arises on the basis of broad outlook, sincere attitude, free thought, conscience and faith. Tolerance is not only a moral duty, but also a political and legal necessity. Tolerance is, first of all, an active attitude formed on the basis of recognition of human rights and freedoms.

Interethnic relations are a process based on the principles of equality, compromise, and cooperation. It is known that religion has a special place in the development of inter-ethnic relations. There are basically two approaches to religion: the first is to believe that religion is a transcendental reality that does not depend on human activity, mind and intellect, and the second is to believe that it is a manifestation of human intelligence and rational research. By the 21st century, these two approaches began to converge on the basis of common cultural values. Concepts such as love, hope, world, justice, equality, consequences, goodness, kindness and tolerance have gained universal importance and created the basis for the harmonization of religious and secular sciences. To conclude from the above, the influence of religious tolerance on inter-ethnic relations is manifested in the following: firstly, religion and religious values do not oppose the ethno-political paradigm, but help to ensure development with their own means and methods. The strategic goal of the ethno-political paradigm concerns all members of society, including believers, confessions, and members of religious organizations; secondly, it is possible to ensure social development when the unity of peoples and nations accepts the strategic goal as its vital goal; thirdly, religious tolerance is

not flattering or giving in to destructive groups, fundamentalism, terrorism and missionary work, it is a reality that can distinguish between positive and negative behavior and ideological views; fourthly, reliance on religion and religious values in interethnic relations is ensured through freedom of conscience. It is a person's constitutional right to believe in what religion, to respect, promote and support what religious values; fifthly, the use of historical-cultural, socio-ethical experiences gathered by religion and religious organizations in inter-ethnic relations is constructive for both sides, especially for social development. But the ethno-political paradigm cannot forget that there are conservative and dogmatic elements in religion, which destructive forces are trying to use.

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Uzbekistan is a multi-ethnic country. Today, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples live in its territory. From the first days of independence, a national policy was developed aimed at interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, and further strengthening of friendship between all peoples living in the territory of Uzbekistan. In January 2017, President Sh. Mirziyoev's speech at the meeting dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the establishment of the Republican International Cultural Center emphasized that international friendship and solidarity are an important factor in the peace and well-being of our people, and consistent attention and care in this field in our country is a sign that it is ongoing.

CONCLUSION

Representatives of all nationalities and peoples living in our country are living in national harmony and harmony, using the equal rights and broad opportunities stipulated in the Constitution and laws, making their due contribution to the development and prosperity of our country. Ensuring inter-ethnic harmony for all peoples and nationalities in our country is strengthened by our Constitution and current laws. Therefore, the main goal of the national policy in our head office is to achieve cohesion and unity of our people as a single nation of Uzbekistan, regardless of ethnic and other characteristics.

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